

FAME

An Open-Source Data Platform for Exploring Metrology Files and More

Malek Atwan¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4484-0354>

¹ Fraunhofer Institute for Electronic Nano Systems, Chemnitz, Germany

² University of Technology Chemnitz, Chemnitz, Germany

*Correspondence: Malek Atwan, malek.atwan@enas.fraunhofer.de

Abstract

Modern development environments, particularly in applied and experimental domains such as semiconductor metrology, face growing demands for managing large volumes of measurement data in structured, interoperable, and reusable ways. However, smaller academic institutions, research transfer organizations, as well as small companies, often still lack access to scalable and affordable research data management (RDM) tools. Instead, they rely on spreadsheets, shared folders, and a lot of human discipline to organize data, leading to inconsistent practices, weak traceability, and limited reuse.

Files & More Explorer (FAME) is a Python-based file storage solution designed to address this gap. It offers a lightweight yet powerful system for storing and organizing measurement files and metadata while aligning with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles [1]. Developed at Fraunhofer ENAS, FAME combines a NoSQL backend (MongoDB) with a configurable file system to accommodate large files and structured metadata. However due to the modular design of FAME if the deploying institute does not use a supported backend, extending FAME to use that institute's backend is very easy, making FAME very extensible. Thus, it supports researchers in organizing their data without requiring a complete overhaul of existing workflows or infrastructure.

FAME enables users to link measurement files (including GB-sized images) with flexible, structured metadata, which is stored in versioned JSON format alongside an event log to capture changes and processing steps. Files and metadata are grouped into logical “entries,” which can be queried through a REST API, a lightweight Python client, or a Shiny-based web interface. This combination provides automated access for developers, scriptable integration for pipelines, and usability for non-programmers.

A unique feature of FAME is its **virtual file system interface**, which allows users to access stored files through customizable folder hierarchies (e.g., /Project/Lot/Wafer/File). This approach supports legacy users accustomed to traditional file navigation while enabling advanced query functionality behind the scenes. It also facilitates adoption in low-infrastructure environments where database fluency is limited.

Figure 1: FAME architecture.

FAME is actively used in a real-world AFM (atomic force microscopy) use case [2], where it automates the ingestion of raw data from instruments, extracts metadata from filenames and structures, and enables downstream analysis. Processed results (such as erosion and dishing metrics) are stored alongside raw images within the same entry, and all events are logged for reproducibility and traceability. The system's performance profiling shows minimal overhead, with most execution time spent on external operations such as database queries or file I/O.

Figure 2: Screenshot from the web-based AFM Dishing Analysis tool showing integration of the FAME Shiny query generator.

FAME is intentionally modular and adaptable. Compared to larger platforms like NOMAD Oasis [3] or LinkAhead [4], it is lighter-weight and focused on serving the specific needs of labs working with large-scale image or measurement files. It can serve as a drop-in RDM layer for research groups with domain-specific metadata and file formats, or as a foundation for more extensive FAIR-compliant data ecosystems. To further align FAME with existing infrastructures and enhance its interoperability and long-term sustainability across disciplines and sectors we seek further use cases from the engineering RDM community.

Keywords: Research Data Infrastructure, Engineering

Resources

FAME is currently in pre-release and is being prepared for open-source publication.

Author contributions

Malek Atwan: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft

Jan Langer: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing

Linda Jäckel: Writing – review & editing

Jörg Schuster: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors thank the Forschungsfabrik Mikroelektronik Deutschland (FMD) for many useful discussions and funding parts of this work in the context of the *FMD Digital 2* project.

Acknowledgement

All authors thank Erik E. Lorenz for the fruitful discussions which paved the way for FAME.

The authors also thank Doreen Hensel for her help in the use case development and FAME testing.

References

- [1] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- [2] A. Zienert, J. Langer, D. Hensel, et al., "Automatic Detection of Via Arrays in AFM Images for CMP Dishing Evaluation," in IEEE Materials for Advanced Metallization Conference (MAM), 2023. DOI: 10.1109/IITC/MAM57687.2023.10154637.
- [3] M. Scheidgen, L. Himanen, A. Ladines, et al., "NOMAD: A distributed web-based platform for managing materials science research data," *Journal of Open Source Software*, DOI: 10.21105/joss.05388.
- [4] D. Hornung, F. Spreckelsen, T. Weiß, "Agile Research Data Management with Open Source: LinkAhead," *ing. grid*, 2024, DOI: 10.48694/inggrid.3866